

INFLUENCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS ON THE FORMATION OF IODINE DEFICIENCY STATES IN CHILDREN AND THEIR CORRECTION

Sharipova Parida Kamilevna

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Associate Professor

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada bolalarda tug'ma tranzitor gipotireoz oqibatlarini davolash samaradorligini o'rganish natijalari ko'rib chiqiladi, tadqiqot natijalari yod tanqisligi holatlarini oldini olish uchun amaliy tibbiyotda qo'llanilishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: tug'ma tranzitor gipotireoz; bolalar; yod tanqisligi; aqliy rivojlanish.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются результаты исследования эффективности лечения последствий транзиторного врождённого гипотиреоза у детей, полученные результаты исследования могут применены в практическом здравоохранении для превенции йоддефицитных состояний.

Ключевые слова: транзиторный гипотиреоз; дети; йоддефицит; психическое развитие.

Abstract. This article discusses the results of a study on the effectiveness of treatment of the consequences of transient congenital hypothyroidism in children; the results of the study can be applied in practical health care for the prevention of iodine deficiency states.

Keywords: transient hypothyroidism; children; iodine deficiency; Psychic development.

Relevance. Numerous studies have established that children living in iodine-deficient areas lag behind their peers in mastering school skills, they have reduced cognitive activity, there is a different degree of insufficiency in the main functions: perception, mental activity, fine motor skills [1,7].

As previously, established, congenital transient hypothyroidism (CTG) has an adverse effect on further physical and mental development, requiring timely correction. CTG can lead to partial underdevelopment of brain systems, disorders of adaptive behavior and higher mental functions, including speech [3,9]. It is also known that injuries in the early stages of ontogenesis cause more pronounced disorders of the development of the central nervous system, especially subcortical formations, while later (peri - and postnatal) ones affect the cerebral cortex to a greater extent [4,8].

According to recent studies, disorders of neuropsychiatric development due to transient hypothyroidism are not amenable to correction by postnatal administration of iodine preparations. The plasticity of the brain of an early child, large potential opportunities to actively respond to changing external stimuli explain the need for early treatment and correction of mental disorders both in children with severe disorders and in children who are at risk for their occurrence [5].

Early prescribing of psychotropic drugs will help to really approach the future capabilities of the child. Psychotropic drugs are widely used because when used correctly, they can improve the functional state of the nervous system, which creates a favorable background for stimulating mental development and developing age-related motor, speech and mental skills. Therapy with psychotropic drugs is used differentially depending on the leading syndrome, taking into account the stimulation of the overall development of functions [2].

All of the above has determined the further **goal** of our study – the effectiveness of complex therapy of developmental disorders of mental functions in children who have undergone VTB.

Materials and methods: indications for treatment were: disorders in the development of psychomotor and perceptual functions, neuropsychiatric development score below 21 points parental consent to treatment.

At the time of treatment initiation, the children were aged from 3 months to 1 year. The results of treatment were controlled by changes in clinical and psychological indicators with an assessment of the CPR in points.

60 children were examined, patients were divided into 2 groups: group 1-30 children received piracetam produced by the company "Gideon Richter". The course of treatment included 10 intramuscular injections of the drug at a dose of 50-70 mg / kg divided into 2 doses in the morning and afternoon, inside, for 6 weeks. Taking into account the presence of hypothyroid conditions in children, a drug of the levothyroxine sodium group, L-thyroxine (Berlin-Chemi), was chosen as replacement therapy. The dose of the drug and the duration of treatment were calculated depending on weight, age, the degree of enlargement and the functional state of the thyroid gland. Dose adjustment was performed together with endocrinologists in short courses (usually 3-4 weeks). Group 2 patients (30 children) received L-thyroxine as monotherapy.

The treatment of mental disorders in children with CTG on an outpatient basis was carried out in a comprehensive manner. Along with the use of piracetam, vitamins for metabolism in the central nervous system were also prescribed, assuming their indispensable participation in carbohydrate metabolism, oxidative processes; (In₁₋₆% 1.0 ml, In₆₋₁% 1.0 ml intramuscularly, every other day for 10 injections; vitamin C-0.1 g-3 times a day) Dehydration therapy was also prescribed. For this purpose, diacarb was used at 0.02 g / kg / day according to the scheme: - 3 days reception – 1 day break, a course of up to 2 weeks, with the addition of potassium preparations. For obvious neurotic symptoms (fear, sharp emotional excitability, fussiness, etc.), small tranquilizers were recommended; elenium 5-10 mg per day, the initial dose was increased to 30 mg if necessary. Seduxen doses ranged from 2.5 to 20 mg.

The results of treatment were controlled by changes in clinical and psychological indicators with an assessment of the coefficient of mental development (CRC) in points. The examination was performed at the beginning of treatment and 3 months after it.

Results of the study: studying the structure of mental disorders in children in both groups in most cases revealed a delay in psychomotor development (71.1% and 66.6%, respectively). Hypo-excitability syndrome accounted for fewer cases in both groups (6.8% and 9.3%, respectively) (Table 1).

Thus, both groups were almost similar in the structure of mental development disorders. This makes it possible to evaluate the effectiveness of the chosen complex treatment of the consequences of congenital transient hypothyroid states. It is necessary to note a decrease in the severity of mental development disorders compared to the period before treatment in both groups.

Table 1. Structure of mental disorders in the examined children with VTG

Disorders	Groups of children			
	First group		Second group	
	Abs*	%	Abs*	%
Hyperexcitability syndrome	6	20	5	16.6

Vegeto-visceral dysfunction	syndrome 3	9.3	2	6.6
Delayed psychomotor development	21	71.1	20	66.6
Hypo-excitability syndrome	2	6.8	3	9.3

Note: * - violations occurred in the same patient, so the absolute sum of the results does not correspond to the number of patients.

As can be seen from Table 2, there was a 1.5-fold decrease in hyperexcitability syndrome in the first group and 1.8-fold in the second group and vegeto-visceral dysfunctions (9-fold and 2-fold, respectively). The acceleration of mental development rates in the first group was almost 3 times, and in the second – 1.3 times.

Table 2. Structure of mental disorders in the examined children with VTG after treatment

Disorders	Groups of children			
	First group		Second group	
	Abs*	%	Abs*	%
Hyperexcitability syndrome	4	13.3	3	9.3
Vegeto-visceral dysfunction	syndrome 0	0	1	3.3
Delayed psychomotor development	8	26.7	15	50
Hypo-excitability syndrome	1	3.3	3	9.3

Note: * - violations occurred in the same patient, so the absolute sum of the results does not correspond to the number of patients.

Positive dynamics in the condition of children who received complex therapy (group 1) were detected quite quickly, and these changes intensified during 6 weeks of treatment.

The advantage of treatment with piracetam in comparison with the second group was also demonstrated by the dynamics of indicators of the coefficient of mental development (CRC). The results of treatment were monitored by changes in clinical and neurological parameters with an assessment of CPR in points.

Fig.1. Dynamics of CPR in children under the influence of treatment

As can be seen from the diagram, there is a significant increase in CPR in group 1 (21.2 ± 1.3 and 25.6 ± 1.4 ; $P < 0.05$), while in group 2 there is a noticeable increase in this indicator (20.1 ± 0.9 and 22.8 ± 1.1 ; $P > 0.05$). This indicates the effectiveness of complex therapy with the appointment of piracetam. The tolerability of piracetam was rated as "good". In two cases (6.7%), during the treatment, increased excitability and irritability were recorded, which were noted at the beginning

of treatment and had a transient character.

As a comparative analysis of neuropsychiatric functions in both groups shows, it was noted that with a slight difference in the results of individual indicators before treatment, an increase in scores occurred only in children who received piracetam. To a greater extent, its effect on improving speech functions, as well as motor skills and behavior was noted, but no direct effect was found on increasing muscle strength in the extremities, reducing hypo-excitability syndrome and timely reduction of physiological reflexes of newborns, reducing the severity of the syndrome of vegeto-visceral dysfunctions.

Thus, complex treatment including piracetam resulted in a more significant increase in the overall CRC, in contrast to the same indicator in children taking only L-thyroxine.

According to some authors, insufficient intake of iodine in the body leads to a congenital violation of higher mental functions, the formation in severe cases of mental retardation, and in mild cases – borderline or partial intellectual disorders [1].

Analysis of the results of treatment showed that in children with CPR below 21 points who received complex treatment with piracetam, it contributed to more pronounced positive changes in mental status, manifested by improved speech and statomotor functions, than in children who received only hormone replacement therapy.

Children who received complex treatment showed significant improvement in motor and behavioral function and an increase in CPR by almost 4 points. It should be noted that the effect of piracetam was manifested on the 14th day of its administration and reached a maximum on the 42nd. Piracetam caused almost no side effects.

Conclusion. Thus, observation of children who have had congenital transient hypothyroidism indicates a lack of neuropsychiatric activity and the need to prescribe nootropic drugs. The optimal effect is observed when using piracetam for 6-8 weeks.

As the assessment of neuropsychiatric functions in children receiving L-thyroxine shows, hormone replacement therapy has a positive effect on the general condition. However, piracetam has a more pronounced effect on the partial functions of intelligence.

Complex therapy with piracetam in children with congenital transient hypothyroidism contributes to the timely correction of identified mental disorders and can be recommended for the prevention of the mental consequences of CTG.

REFERENCES

1. Л.Б. Нугманова, ШТ Муратова, РБ Абдазова, ММ Атаджанова, ФК Шарипова Перинатальные аспекты и тиреоидный статус новорожденных от узбекской популяции женщин с тиреоидитом хаото в стадии гипотиреоза // Международный эндокринологический журнал, 2011, с. 27-30.
2. Шарипова Ф.К. Психический онтогенез детей, перенесших врождённый транзиторный гипотиреоз в периоде новорожденности // Врач-аспирант, 2014; с. 235-240.
3. Alevizaki M, Mantzou E, Cimponeriu AT et al. Evidence for tissue hypothyroidism in treated hypothyroid patients with "euthyroid" TSH levels. J. Endocrinol. Invest., 2002, 25(Sup7):083.
4. Accuracy of ultrasonography to establish the diagnosis and aetiology of permanent primary congenital hypothyroidism / Kreisner E., Camargo-Neto E., Maia C.R., Gross J.L. // Clin Endocrinol. – 2003. – vol. 59. – N3. – P. 361-5.
5. Biondi B, Palmieri E, Lombardi G, Fazio S. Effects of subclinical thyroid dysfunction on the heart. Ann Intern Med, 2002, 137: 904-914.

6. Children’s turn-arounds in psychotherapy: the doctor’s gesture / L.C. Terr, G. Fox et al. // Psychoanal Study Child. – 2006. – vol.61. – P. 56-81.
7. Domenech Martinez E., Barroso Guerrero F. Utility of congenital hypothyroidism screening in neonates for monitoring iodine deficit disorders in the Canary Islands (Spain) // An Pediatr. – 2003. – vol. 58. – N4. – P. 357-63.
8. Evolving hypopituitarism as a consequence of traumatic brain injury (TBI) in childhood – call for attention / S. Pekic, N. Curic et al. // Endocrine. – 2007. – vol.31. – N3. – P. 268-71.
9. Iodine deficiency disorders in Europe / Vitti P., Rago T., Aghini-Lombardi F., Pinchera A. // Public Health Nutr. – 2001. – vol. 4. – P. 529-35.
10. Singh N, Weisler SL, Hershman JM. The acute effect of calcium carbonate on the intestinal absorption of levothyroxine. Thyroid: official journal of the American Thyroid Association, 2000, 11: 967-971.
11. Zamfirescu I, Carlson HE. Absorption of levothyroxine when coadministered with various calcium formulations. Thyroid: official journal of the American Thyroid Association, 2011, 21: 483-486.